

D1.1 Project Handbook

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Description	This report describes all operational aspects of the project, project execution and management in order to provide the consortium partners with background information about specific procedures and norms to be followed during the project lifetime. Quality procedures, risk identification, management and mitigation procedures, as well as guidelines on knowledge management for information sharing.		
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Abstract

This report describes all operational aspects of the project, project execution and management in order to provide the consortium partners with background information about specific procedures and norms to be followed during the project lifetime. Quality procedures, risk identification, management and mitigation procedures, as well as guidelines on knowledge management for information sharing.

Statement of originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

Table of contents

TABLE OF CONTENTS	3
LIST OF TABLES	5
LIST OF FIGURES	6
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	7
1 INTRODUCTION	8
1.1 PURPOSE OF THIS DOCUMENT	8
1.2 STRUCTURE OF THE DOCUMENT	8
1.3 GLOSSARY ADOPTED IN THIS DOCUMENT	8
2 PROJECT OVERVIEW	10
2.1 PROJECT IDENTIFICATION	10
2.2 PROJECT SUMMARY	10
2.3 OVERALL WORKPLAN	11
2.3.1 <i>Work Package list</i>	11
2.3.2 <i>Milestones</i>	12
2.3.3 <i>Gantt</i>	14
2.4 PROJECT REPRESENTATIVES	15
3 PROJECT RESOURCES	16
3.1 EFFORTS PER WORKPACKAGE	16
3.2 EFFORTS PER PROJECT PERIOD	17
3.3 PROJECT MANAGEMENT PLAN	17
3.3.1 <i>WP1: Project Management</i>	18
3.3.2 <i>WP2: Human-centric design</i>	20
3.3.3 <i>WP3: Federated Learning and Continual Learning</i>	22
3.3.4 <i>WP4: Modelling and optimisation</i>	23
3.3.5 <i>WP5: Validation and replication</i>	25
3.3.6 <i>WP6: Exploitation, dissemination and environmental impact</i>	28
4 PROJECT MANAGEMENT	31
4.1 PROJECT GOVERNANCE.....	31
4.1.1 <i>Management Structure and Procedures</i>	31
4.1.2 <i>Decision making process</i>	32
4.1.3 <i>Conflict resolution</i>	33
4.2 PROJECT COMMUNICATION	34
4.2.1 <i>Contact lists</i>	34
4.2.2 <i>Email and emailing lists</i>	35
4.2.3 <i>Conferencing system</i>	36
4.2.4 <i>Project repository</i>	37
4.2.5 <i>Meetings and procedures</i>	38
4.3 PROJECT MONITORING	40
4.4 TECHNICAL MONITORING	41
4.4.1 <i>Technical KPIs table</i>	41

4.4.2	<i>How to fill the table</i>	42
4.5	CONTRACTUAL MANAGEMENT	43
4.6	ADMINISTRATIVE AND FINANCIAL REPORTING.....	43
4.6.1	<i>Reporting to the EC</i>	43
4.6.2	<i>Internal Interim Activity Reports (IAR)</i>	44
4.6.3	<i>Financial reporting</i>	46
4.6.4	<i>Budget & payments</i>	46
5	QUALITY ASSURANCE	47
5.1	DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT PROCESS	47
5.1.1	<i>Documents language</i>	47
5.1.2	<i>Documents storage</i>	47
5.1.3	<i>Documents nomenclature</i>	48
5.1.4	<i>Bibliographical references</i>	48
5.1.5	<i>Documents templates</i>	48
5.2	QUALITY GUIDELINES ON DELIVERABLES PRODUCTION	49
5.2.1	<i>Legibility</i>	49
5.2.2	<i>Readability</i>	49
5.2.3	<i>Comprehension</i>	50
5.3	DELIVERABLES REVIEW	50
5.3.1	<i>Internal review planning</i>	50
5.3.2	<i>Roles and responsibilities</i>	51
5.3.3	<i>Deliverable review process</i>	52
5.3.4	<i>Deliverable review process responsibility matrix</i>	54
6	RISK MANAGEMENT	56
6.1	RISK MANAGEMENT PROCESSES.....	56
6.2	PLAN RISK MANAGEMENT	57
6.2.1	<i>Risk Categories</i>	57
6.2.2	<i>Roles and Responsibilities</i>	57
6.2.3	<i>Definitions of probability and impact</i>	58
6.2.4	<i>Risk Register</i>	59
6.3	IDENTIFY RISKS	62
6.4	RISK ANALYSIS.....	62
6.5	PLAN RISK RESPONSES	63
6.6	CONTROL RISKS	63
6.7	COMMON RISK MANAGEMENT ERRORS	64
	REFERENCES	65
APPENDIX A	ACRONYMS	66
APPENDIX A	INTERNAL REVIEW PLANNING	67
APPENDIX B	PEER REVIEW FORM	68

List of tables

TABLE 1: PROJECT IDENTIFICATION	10
TABLE 2: WORK PACKAGE LIST.....	11
TABLE 3: PROJECT MILESTONES.....	12
TABLE 4: PROJECT REPRESENTATIVES.....	15
TABLE 5: EFFORTS PER WP.....	16
TABLE 6: LINEAR EFFORTS PER PERIOD	17
TABLE 7: WP1: GENERAL INFORMATION	18
TABLE 8: T1.1: GENERAL INFORMATION	18
TABLE 9: T1.2: GENERAL INFORMATION.....	18
TABLE 10: T1.3: GENERAL INFORMATION	19
TABLE 11: T1.4: GENERAL INFORMATION	19
TABLE 12: T1.5: GENERAL INFORMATION.....	19
TABLE 13: WP2: GENERAL INFORMATION	20
TABLE 14: T2.1: GENERAL INFORMATION.....	20
TABLE 15: T2.2: GENERAL INFORMATION	20
TABLE 16: T2.3: GENERAL INFORMATION.....	21
TABLE 17: T2.4: GENERAL INFORMATION	21
TABLE 18: T2.5: GENERAL INFORMATION.....	21
TABLE 19: WP3: GENERAL INFORMATION.....	22
TABLE 20: T3.1: GENERAL INFORMATION.....	22
TABLE 21: T3.2: GENERAL INFORMATION	22
TABLE 22: T3.3: GENERAL INFORMATION.....	23
TABLE 23: WP4: GENERAL INFORMATION.....	23
TABLE 24: T4.1: GENERAL INFORMATION	23
TABLE 25: T4.2: GENERAL INFORMATION	24
TABLE 26: T4.3: GENERAL INFORMATION	24
TABLE 27: T4.4: GENERAL INFORMATION	25
TABLE 28: WP5: GENERAL INFORMATION	25
TABLE 29: T5.1: GENERAL INFORMATION.....	26
TABLE 30: T5.2: GENERAL INFORMATION.....	26
TABLE 31: T5.3: GENERAL INFORMATION.....	27
TABLE 32: T5.4: GENERAL INFORMATION	27
TABLE 33: T5.5: GENERAL INFORMATION	28
TABLE 34: WP6: GENERAL INFORMATION	28
TABLE 35: T6. 1: GENERAL INFORMATION	28
TABLE 36: T6. 2: GENERAL INFORMATION.....	29
TABLE 37: T6. 3: GENERAL INFORMATION.....	29
TABLE 38: T6. 4: GENERAL INFORMATION.....	30

TABLE 39: PARTNERS ROLES.....	32
TABLE 40: ALCHIMIA MAILING LISTS.....	35
TABLE 41: PROJECT MANAGEMENT KPIS	41
TABLE 42: ALCHIMIA TECHNICAL MANAGEMENT KPIS TEMPLATE.....	42
TABLE 43: EXAMPLE OF TIMELINE REPORTING.....	45
TABLE 44: IARS SCHEDULE	46
TABLE 45: ROLES AND RESPONSIBILITIES ON DELIVERABLE REVIEW	51
TABLE 46: REVIEW PROCESS MAIN PROCESS.....	53
TABLE 47: REVIEW PROCESS STEPS	53
TABLE 48: REVIEW PROCESS RESPONSIBILITY MATRIX	55
TABLE 49: ROLES AND RESPONSIBILITIES – RISK MGT	57
TABLE 50: SCALE OF PROBABILITY.....	58
TABLE 51: IMPACT ON SCHEDULE	59
TABLE 52: IMPACT ON RESULTS.....	59
TABLE 53: ALCHIMIA RISK REGISTER FIELDS	60
TABLE 54: ALCHIMIA RISK REGISTER.....	61

List of figures

FIGURE 1 – ALCHIMIA PROJECT GANTT.....	14
FIGURE 2 – ALCHIMIA MANAGEMENT STRUCTURE	31
FIGURE 3 – DECISION MAKING PROCESS.....	32
FIGURE 4 – ALCHIMIA REPOSITORY STRUCTURE	37
FIGURE 5 – REPORTING FLOW.....	45
FIGURE 6 – DELIVERABLE REVIEW PROCESS.....	52
FIGURE 7 – RISK MANAGEMENT PROCESSES CYCLE.....	56
FIGURE 8 – ALCHIMIA REVIEWERS SPREADSHEET CAPTURE.....	67
FIGURE 9 – ALCHIMIA PEER REVIEW FORM.....	68

Executive Summary

This document is the deliverable D1.1 Project Handbook and it contains the procedures for internal management of the project, describes in detail the risk management process and define internal QA procedures. .

In this report, the whole management strategy is presented, including the communication procedures and the tools to keep a clear and transparent knowledge of everything that is happening in the execution of the project. Risk management strategy and quality plan are also presented; the mechanisms to guarantee the highest quality in the different ALCHIMIA results are also described in this document. Quality guidelines, as well as quality review process, are clearly detailed in this document. The risk methodology to follow is also described in this report.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of this document

The present document is the Project Handbook for the ALCHIMIA project. This document has two main goals: first it defines common management procedures for the internal management of the project, such as the consortium governance, project monitoring and project reporting; and second it defines the quality plan and risk management plan for the project.

The procedures for the internal management of the project are aligned with the approved documents by the consortium and European Commission (EC), namely the Consortium Agreement (CA) and the Grant Agreement (GA).

The quality and risk management plan defined in this document aims at ensuring that the quality expected by the EC on the results of the project are achieved and any risks are previously identified and appropriately mitigated if so required.

The management/quality/innovation management procedures that are here described follow ATOS methodology defined and applied in all Horizon Europe projects coordinated by ATOS. This methodology has been adapted to the characteristics of ALCHIMIA project

1.2 Structure of the document

This document is divided into four main sections:

- Chapter 2 and 3 describe the project at a high level, including its workplan and resources planned.
- Chapter 4 - Project Management: it describes the management procedures to be followed in this project in order to achieve both the technical and administrative objectives.
- Chapter 5 - Quality Assurance: it defines the processes to monitor and control the production of results in order to meet an adequate level of quality.
- Chapter 6 - Risk Management: it defines the processes in charge of identifying, assess, control, and mitigate all risks that could jeopardize the project expected results.

1.3 Glossary adopted in this document

- Identify risks. The process of determining which risks may affect the project and documenting their characteristics. [1]
- Control risks: The process of implementing risk response plans, tracking identified risks, monitoring residual risks, identifying new risks, and evaluating risk process effectiveness throughout the project. [1]
- Plan risk Management: The process of defining how to conduct risk management activities for a project. [1]
- Plan risk responses: The process of developing options and actions to enhance opportunities and to reduce threats to project objectives. [1]
- Risk: An uncertain event or condition that, if it occurs, has a positive or negative effect on one or more project objectives. [1]

- Risk Avoidance: A risk response strategy whereby the project team acts to eliminate the threat. [1]
- Risk categorization: Organization by sources of risk, the area of the project affected, or other useful category (e.g., project phase) to determine the areas of the project most exposed to the effects of uncertainty. [1]
- Risk category: A group of potential causes of risk. [1]
- Risk Management Plan: A component of the project management plan that describes how risk management activities will be structured and performed. [1]
- Risk Mitigation: A risk response strategy whereby the project team acts to reduce the probability of occurrence or impact of a risk. [1]
- Risk reassessment: Risk reassessment is the identification of new risks, reassessment of current risks, and the closing of risks that are outdated. [1]
- Risk register: A document in which the results of risk analysis and risk response planning are recorded. [1]
- Legibility: The quality of making readers able to see, discriminate, and recognize the characters and words in your text. Legibility is thus mainly determined by visual design, specifically typography. [2][3]
- Readability: The quality of writing and language use that makes text easy to read and content to understand. [2][3]
- Comprehension: Measures whether a user can understand the intended meaning of a text and can draw the correct conclusions from the text. [2][3]

2 Project Overview

2.1 Project Identification

Table 1: Project Identification

Project Acronym	ALCHIMIA
Project Title	Data and decentralized Artificial intelligence for a competitive and green European metallurgy industry
Project Type	HORIZON-IA
Call	HORIZON-CL4-2021-DIGITAL-EMERGING-01
Topic	HORIZON-CL4-2021-DIGITAL-EMERGING-01-09 - AI, Data and Robotics for the Green Deal
Contract	101070046
Project Start Date	01/09/2022
Project End Date	31/08/2025
Estimated Total Time	36 Months
Estimated Efforts	505 PMs
CORDIS Fiche	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101070046

2.2 Project Summary

Energy-intensive industries, embedded in many strategic value chains, make up more than half of the energy consumption of the European industry and reducing their CO₂ intensity is crucial for meeting the objectives of the Paris agreement. Within EILs, metallurgy poses a major challenge due to the trade-off that must be found between maintaining economic profitability, while progressively implementing the required transformations for a greener production. While digitalisation is generating a data deluge, Artificial Intelligence cannot be fully adopted due to limitations to share data between several factories and the heterogeneity of systems that hinders the replicability of AI.

ALCHIMIA aims to build a platform based on Federated Learning and Continual Learning to help big European metallurgy industries unlock the full potential of AI to support the needed transformations to create high-quality, competitive, efficient and green manufacturing processes. The project will address the challenges of the steel sector, creating an innovative system that automates and optimises the production process dynamically with a holistic approach that includes scrap recycling and steelmaking. ALCHIMIA will find an optimal mix to reduce energy consumption, emissions and waste generation of steelmaking while guaranteeing to obtain high-quality products. The

replicability and scalability of ALCHIMIA will be enabled through a complementary use case for the manufacturing of automotive parts. The developed system will be used for prognostic optimisation of the mix of input materials charged in the furnaces to obtain a certain product quality that matches the customers' specifications while reducing the environmental impact and the energy consumption. ALCHIMIA will not only seek the optimal mix for the charge of metallurgy furnace, it will also determine the best combination of learning capacities to enable a smooth green transition for all industries thanks to unprecedented collaboration.

2.3 Overall Workplan

2.3.1 Work Package list

The project workflow is orchestrated around 6 Work Packages, as indicated in the following table:

Table 2: Work Package list

WP Number	WP Title	Lead Beneficiary	Person Months	Start Month	End Month
1	Project Management	1 - ATOS IT	32	1	36
2	Human-centric design	8 - CAR	79	1	27
3	Federated Learning and Continual Learning	1 - ATOS IT	71	3	30
4	Modelling and optimisation	2 - SSSA	121	3	24
5	Validation and replication	4 - CEL	117	1	36
6	Exploitation, dissemination and environmental impact	7 - MI	85	1	36
TOTAL			505		

2.3.2 Milestones

The following table summarizes the project milestones, which are key control points of the project execution:

Table 3: Project Milestones

Milestone Nr.	Milestone title	WP Num.	Lead Beneficiary	Due Date	Means of verification
1	Kick-Off	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6	1 – ATOS IT	1	Signature of Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement; project team, role and responsibilities clearly defined; project activities planning clearly defined
2	Branding	6	7 – MI	3	Publication of ALCHIMIA website, availability of communication material
3	ALCHIMIA outreach and standardisation plan	6	3 – BFI	6	Outreach and standardisation plan of the project, with relevant inputs from the consortium
4	Requirements, detailed architecture, industrial use-cases preparation	2, 5	4 – CEL	12	User stories created in the product backlog, diagrams for use-cases and architecture, industrial use-cases ready for the integration
5	ALCHIMIA alpha MVP	3, 4	1 – ATOS IT	12	Source code available
6	Integration and validation of ALCHIMIA in industrial use-cases. V1	2, 5	4 – CEL	18	ALCHIMIA technical components integrated into the three projects' use-cases. Initial evaluation and extraction of KPIs
7	Preliminary environmental impact assessment	6	2 – SSSA	18	Preliminary environmental impact assessment of ALCHIMIA with the participation of the consortium

Milestone Nr.	Milestone title	WP Num.	Lead Beneficiary	Due Date	Means of verification
8	IPR management and business models	6	7 - MI	22	Identification of background and foreground, the initial version of business models for exploitation of assets
9	ALCHIMIA MVP beta	2, 3, 4	1 - ATOS IT	24	Source code available
10	Validation of ALCHIMIA industrial cases. V2	2, 5	4 - CEL	27	Second round for the validation of ALCHIMIA results. Updates of the project's KPIs
11	ALCHIMIA MVP gold	2, 3, 4	1 - ATOS IT	33	Source code available
12	Validation of ALCHIMIA industrial cases. Final.	5	4 - CEL	36	Final validation of ALCHIMIA results. Updates of the project's KPIs
13	ALCHIMIA exploitation agreement	6	7 - MI	36	Sustainability and exploitation plan

2.3.3 Gantt

WP	Title	Leader	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	
WP1	Project management	ATOS																																					
Task 1.1	Project steering	ATOS																																					
Task 1.2	Quality assurance and risk management	ATOS																																					
Task 1.3	Project reporting and financial matters	ATOS																																					
Task 1.4	Technical coordination	BFI																																					
Task 1.5	Data, ethics and compliance	SSA																																					
WP2	Human-centric design	CAR																																					
Task 2.1	Requirements analysis, use-cases definition and KPIs	CEL																																					
Task 2.2	Sector technology landscape	CAR																																					
Task 2.3	Ex Ante evaluation	CAR																																					
Task 2.4	Reference architecture design and specification	ATOS																																					
Task 2.5	Training programme	CAR																																					
WP3	Federated Learning and Continual Learning	ATOS																																					
Task 3.1	Federated Learning infrastructure implementation	ATOS																																					
Task 3.2	Continual Learning	ATOS																																					
Task 3.3	Transfer learning and adaption	ATOS																																					
WP4	Modelling and optimisation	SSSA																																					
Task 4.1	Data collection, fusion and curation	EXUS																																					
Task 4.2	Models development	BFI																																					
Task 4.3	LCA framework	SSSA																																					
Task 4.4	Optimisation framework	SSSA																																					
WP5	Validation and replication	CEL																																					
Task 5.1	Detailed specification of scenarios and end-user sites preparation	CEL																																					
Task 5.2	Integration, deployment and validation	CEL																																					
Task 5.3	Human and social impact E-Post evaluation	CAR																																					
Task 5.4	Techno-economic feedback and evaluation	FDT																																					
Task 5.5	Probing and assessing contribution to the Green Deal	SSSA																																					
WP6	Exploitation, dissemination and environmental impact	M																																					
Task 6.1	Strategy for Impact Creation and Content	M																																					
Task 6.2	Standardisation	BFI																																					
Task 6.3	Environmental Impact Assessment	M																																					
Task 6.4	Business Exploitation and Sustainability	M																																					

Figure 1 – ALCHIMIA Project Gantt

2.4 Project Representatives

Table 4: Project representatives

N°	Acronym	Partner	Country	Roles
1	ATOS IT	ATOS IT SOLUTIONS AND SERVICES IBERIA SL	ES	Project Coordinator Quality Manager WP1 & WP3 Leader Steering Committee member
2	SSSA	SCUOLA SUPERIORE DI STUDI UNIVERSITARI E DI PERFEZIONAMENTO S ANNA	IT	Ethics Manager WP4 Leader Steering Committee member
3	BFI	VDEH-BETRIEBSFORSCHUNGSINSTITUT GMBH	DE	Technical Coordinator Steering Committee member
4	CEL	CELSA FRANCE	FR	WP5 Leader Steering Committee member
4.1	CEL-BCN	COMPANIA ESPANOLA DE LAMINACION SL	ES	Affiliated Entity
4.2	CEL-PL	CELSA HUTA OSTROWIEC SP Z OO	PL	Affiliated Entity
5	EXUS	EXUS SOFTWARE MONOPROSOPI ETAIRIA PERIORISMENIS EVTHINIS	EL	Beneficiary
6	FDT	FONDERIA DI TORBOLE S.R.L.	IT	Beneficiary
7	MI	MANDAT INTERNATIONAL ALIAS FONDATION POUR LA COOPERATION INTERNATIONALE	CH	Associated Partner Exploitation Manager WP6 Leader Steering Committee member
8	CAR	CARDIFF UNIVERSITY	UK	Associated Partner WP2 Leader Steering Committee member

3 Project Resources

This section summarizes the project personnel resources, measured in person-months. Other project resources, such as development tools, code repository, the project communication infrastructure, or any supporting means are described in later sections of the document.

3.1 Efforts per Workpackage

This section provides an overview of the total effort allocation according to the work breakdown structure of the project. The WP effort matches the effort stated in the GA.

Table 5: Efforts per WP

Nº	Partner	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	TOTAL
1	ATOS IT	22.00	12.00	39.00	19.00	12.00	8.00	112.00
2	SSSA	6.00	3.00	4.00	38.00	20.00	7.00	78.00
3	BFI	4.00	3.00	6.00	19.00	6.00	9.00	47.00
4	CEL		12.00	7.00	8.00	25.00	10.00	62.00
4.1	CEL-BCN		4.00	1.50	1.50	6.00	1.00	14.00
4.2	CEL-PL		2.00	1.50	1.50	4.00	1.00	10.00
5	EXUS		3.00	8.00	19.00	9.00	7.00	46.00
6	FDT		14.00	4.00	11.00	23.00	8.00	60.00
7	MI		3.00		4.00	6.00	29.00	42.00
8	CAR		23.00			6.00	5.00	34.00
TOTAL PMs		32.00	79.00	71.00	121.00	117.00	85.00	505.00

3.2 Efforts per project period

This section provides an initial estimation of the partners' effort distributed along the project tranches. This estimation is the base for monitoring and controlling the resources consumption in the interim reporting dates agreed in the CA, happening every 6 months, and for the official periodic reports. The estimation assumes a uniform and linear effort spent and consistent dedication over the duration of each task.

Table 6: Linear Efforts per period

Period	Months	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	TOTAL
P1	M01 - M06	5.33	17.56	10.14	22.00	19.50	14.17	88.70
	M07 - M12	5.33	17.56	15.21	33.00	19.50	14.17	104.77
	M13 - M18	5.33	17.56	15.21	33.00	19.50	14.17	104.77
P2	M19 - M24	5.33	17.56	15.21	33.00	19.50	14.17	104.77
	M25 - M30	5.33	8.78	15.21	0.00	19.50	14.17	62.99
	M31 - M36	5.33	0.00	0.00	0.00	19.50	14.17	39.00
TOTAL PMs		32.00	79.00	71.00	121.00	117.00	85.00	505.00

3.3 Project Management Plan

This section provides an overview of the work breakdown structure of the project.

Below each WP is summarized, each task provides the following information:

- Leaders. Appointment of particular organization and contact person for each duty in the task, including the task itself, potential sub-tasks and deliverables.
- Start and End dates.
- Schedule. Time plan and milestones related with each WP/Task/Sub-task.
- Deliverables. All documents to be produced by each task.

3.3.1 WP1: Project Management

Table 7: WP1: General Information

Lead Beneficiary	ATOS IT		
WP Leader	Diego Esteban		
Start Month	M1	End Month	M36

3.3.1.1 Task 1.1: Project Steering

Table 8: T1.1: General Information

Lead Beneficiary	ATOS IT		
Task Leader	Diego Esteban		
Start Month	M1	End Month	M36
Deliverables produced by the task	D1.1.- Project Handbook – Due: M3		
Related Milestones	MS1.- Kick-Off (KO) – Due: M1		

3.3.1.2 Task 1.2: Quality assurance and risk management

Table 9: T1.2: General Information

Lead Beneficiary	ATOS IT		
Task Leader	Diego Esteban		
Start Month	M1	End Month	M36
Deliverables produced by the task	D1.1.- Project Handbook – Due: M3		
Related Milestones	MS1.- Kick-Off (KO) – Due: M1		

3.3.1.3 Task 1.3: Project reporting and financial matters

Table 10: T1.3: General Information

Lead Beneficiary	ATOS IT		
Task Leader	Diego Esteban		
Start Month	M1	End Month	M36
Deliverables produced by the task	D1.1.- Project Handbook – Due: M3		
Related Milestones	MS1.- Kick-Off (KO) – Due: M1		

3.3.1.4 Task 1.4: Technical Coordination

Table 11: T1.4: General Information

Lead Beneficiary	ATOS IT		
Task Leader	Diego Esteban		
Start Month	M1	End Month	M36
Deliverables produced by the task	No deliverables associated to this task		
Related Milestones	No milestones associated to this task		

3.3.1.5 Task 1.5: Data, Ethics and Compliance

Table 12: T1.5: General Information

Lead Beneficiary	ATOS IT		
Task Leader	Diego Esteban		
Start Month	M1	End Month	M36
Deliverables produced by the task	D1.2 – Data Management Plan – Due: M6		
Related Milestones	No milestones associated to this task		

3.3.2 WP2: Human-centric design

Table 13: WP2: General Information

Lead Beneficiary	CAR		
WP Leader	Dean Stroud		
Start Month	M1	End Month	M27

3.3.2.1 Task 2.1: Requirements' analysis, use-cases definition and KPIs

Table 14: T2.1: General Information

Lead Beneficiary	CEL		
Task Leader	Jordi Gálvez		
Start Month	M1	End Month	M12
Deliverables produced by the task	D2.1.- Requirements and human-centric recommendations – Due: M12		
Related Milestones	MS4.- Requirements, detailed architecture, industrial use-cases preparation – Due: M12		

3.3.2.2 Task 2.2: Sector technology landscape

Table 15: T2.2: General Information

Lead Beneficiary	CAR		
Task Leader	Dean Stroud		
Start Month	M1	End Month	M4
Deliverables produced by the task	D2.2.- ALCHIMIA architecture – Due: M24		
Related Milestones	MS4.- Requirements, detailed architecture, industrial use-cases preparation – Due: M12		

3.3.2.3 Task 2.3: Ex Ante evaluation

Table 16: T2.3: General Information

Lead Beneficiary	CAR		
Task Leader	Dean Stroud		
Start Month	M5	End Month	M12
Deliverables produced by the task	D2.1.- Requirements and human-centric recommendations – Due: M12		
Related Milestones	MS4.- Requirements, detailed architecture, industrial use-cases preparation – Due: M12		

3.3.2.4 Task 2.4: Reference architecture design and specification

Table 17: T2.4: General Information

Lead Beneficiary	ATOS		
Task Leader	Daniel Calvo		
Start Month	M5	End Month	M24
Deliverables produced by the task	D2.2.- ALCHIMIA architecture – Due: M24		
Related Milestones	MS4.- Requirements, detailed architecture, industrial use-cases preparation – Due: M12		

3.3.2.5 Task 2.5: Training programme

Table 18: T2.5: General Information

Lead Beneficiary	CAR		
Task Leader	Dean Stroud		
Start Month	M13	End Month	M27
Deliverables produced by the task	D2.3.- Training programme – Due: M27		
Related Milestones	MS4.- Requirements, detailed architecture, industrial use-cases preparation – Due: M12		

3.3.3 WP3: Federated Learning and Continual Learning

Table 19: WP3: General Information

Lead Beneficiary	ATOS		
WP Leader	Daniel Calvo		
Start Month	M3	End Month	M30

3.3.3.1 Task 3.1: Federated Learning infrastructure implementation

Table 20: T3.1: General Information

Lead Beneficiary	ATOS		
Task Leader	Daniel Calvo		
Start Month	M3	End Month	M18
Deliverables produced by the task	D3.1.- Federated Learning framework_version 1 – Due: M12 D3.2.- Federated Learning framework_final version – Due: M30		
Related Milestones	MS5.- ALCHIMIA alpha MVP – Due: M12 MS9.- ALCHIMIA beta MVP – Due: M24 MS11.- ALCHIMIA gold MVP – Due: M33		

3.3.3.2 Task 3.2: Continual learning

Table 21: T3.2: General Information

Lead Beneficiary	ATOS		
Task Leader	Daniel Calvo		
Start Month	M6	End Month	M24
Deliverables produced by the task	D3.1.- Federated Learning framework_version 1 – Due: M12 D3.2.- Federated Learning framework_final version – Due: M30		
Related Milestones	MS5.- ALCHIMIA alpha MVP – Due: M12 MS9.- ALCHIMIA beta MVP – Due: M24 MS11.- ALCHIMIA gold MVP – Due: M33		

3.3.3.3 Task 3.3: Transfer learning and adaption

Table 22: T3.3: General Information

Lead Beneficiary	ATOS		
Task Leader	Daniel Calvo		
Start Month	M13	End Month	M30
Deliverables produced by the task	D3.1.- Federated Learning framework_version 1 – Due: M12 D3.2.- Federated Learning framework_final version – Due: M30		
Related Milestones	MS5.- ALCHIMIA alpha MVP – Due: M12 MS9.- ALCHIMIA beta MVP – Due: M24 MS11.- ALCHIMIA gold MVP – Due: M33		

3.3.4 WP4: Modelling and optimisation

Table 23: WP4: General Information

Lead Beneficiary	SSSA		
WP Leader	Valentina Colla		
Start Month	M3	End Month	M24

3.3.4.1 Task 4.1: Data collection, fusion and curation

Table 24: T4.1: General Information

Lead Beneficiary	EXUS		
Task Leader	Marcos Varveris		
Start Month	M3	End Month	M18
Deliverables produced by the task	D4.1 - Holistic process models and XAI – Due: M18		
Related Milestones	MS5.- ALCHIMIA alpha MVP – Due: M12 MS9.- ALCHIMIA beta MVP – Due: M24 MS11.- ALCHIMIA gold MVP – Due: M33		

3.3.4.2 Task 4.2: Models development

Table 25: T4.2: General Information

Lead Beneficiary	BFI		
Task Leader	Waldemar Krieger		
Start Month	M6	End Month	M24
Deliverables produced by the task	D4.1 - Holistic process models and XAI – Due: M18		
Related Milestones	MS5.- ALCHIMIA alpha MVP – Due: M12 MS9.- ALCHIMIA beta MVP – Due: M24 MS11.- ALCHIMIA gold MVP – Due: M33		

3.3.4.3 Task 4.3: LCA Framework

Table 26: T4.3: General Information

Lead Beneficiary	SSSA		
Task Leader	Valentina Colla		
Start Month	M6	End Month	M24
Deliverables produced by the task	D4.2 - LCA and optimisation frameworks – Due: M24		
Related Milestones	MS5.- ALCHIMIA alpha MVP – Due: M12 MS9.- ALCHIMIA beta MVP – Due: M24 MS11.- ALCHIMIA gold MVP – Due: M33		

3.3.4.4 Task 4.4: Optimisation framework

Table 27: T4.4: General Information

Lead Beneficiary	SSSA		
Task Leader	Valentina Colla		
Start Month	M13	End Month	M24
Deliverables produced by the task	D4.2 - LCA and optimisation frameworks – Due: M24		
Related Milestones	MS5.- ALCHIMIA alpha MVP – Due: M12 MS9.- ALCHIMIA beta MVP – Due: M24 MS11.- ALCHIMIA gold MVP – Due: M33		

3.3.5 WP5: Validation and replication

Table 28: WP5: General Information

Lead Beneficiary	CEL		
WP Leader	Jordi Gálvez		
Start Month	M1	End Month	M36

3.3.5.1 Task 5.1: Detailed specification of scenarios and end-user sites preparation

Table 29: T5.1: General Information

Lead Beneficiary	CEL		
Task Leader	Jordi Gálvez		
Start Month	M1	End Month	M12
Deliverables produced by the task	D5.1 - Use-cases preparation – Due: M12		
Related Milestones	MS6.- Integration and validation of ALCHIMIA in industrial use-cases. V1 – Due: M18 MS10.- Integration and validation of ALCHIMIA in industrial use-cases. V2 – Due: M27 MS12.- Integration and validation of ALCHIMIA in industrial use-cases. Final – Due: M36		

3.3.5.2 Task 5.2: Integration, deployment and validation

Table 30: T5.2: General Information

Lead Beneficiary	CEL		
Task Leader	Jordi Gálvez		
Start Month	M12	End Month	M33
Deliverables produced by the task	D5.2 - Integration, validation and evaluation in ALCHIMIA use-cases – Due: M36		
Related Milestones	MS6.- Integration and validation of ALCHIMIA in industrial use-cases. V1 – Due: M18 MS10.- Integration and validation of ALCHIMIA in industrial use-cases. V2 – Due: M27 MS12.- Integration and validation of ALCHIMIA in industrial use-cases. Final – Due: M36		

3.3.5.3 Task 5.3: Human and social impact E-Post evaluation

Table 31: T5.3: General Information

Lead Beneficiary	CAR		
Task Leader	Dean Stroud		
Start Month	M25	End Month	M36
Deliverables produced by the task	D5.2 - Integration, validation and evaluation in ALCHIMIA use-cases – Due: M36		
Related Milestones	MS6.- Integration and validation of ALCHIMIA in industrial use-cases. V1 – Due: M18 MS10.- Integration and validation of ALCHIMIA in industrial use-cases. V2 – Due: M27 MS12.- Integration and validation of ALCHIMIA in industrial use-cases. Final – Due: M36		

3.3.5.4 Task 5.4: Techno-economic feedback end evaluation

Table 32: T5.4: General Information

Lead Beneficiary	FDT		
Task Leader	Laura Forlani		
Start Month	M18	End Month	M36
Deliverables produced by the task	D5.2 - Integration, validation and evaluation in ALCHIMIA use-cases – Due: M36		
Related Milestones	MS6.- Integration and validation of ALCHIMIA in industrial use-cases. V1 – Due: M18 MS10.- Integration and validation of ALCHIMIA in industrial use-cases. V2 – Due: M27 MS12.- Integration and validation of ALCHIMIA in industrial use-cases. Final – Due: M36		

3.3.5.5 Task 5.5: Probing and assessing contribution to the Green Deal

Table 33: T5.5: General Information

Lead Beneficiary	SSSA		
Task Leader	Valentina Colla		
Start Month	M18	End Month	M36
Deliverables produced by the task	D5.2 - Integration, validation and evaluation in ALCHIMIA use-cases – Due: M36		
Related Milestones	MS6.- Integration and validation of ALCHIMIA in industrial use-cases. V1 – Due: M18 MS10.- Integration and validation of ALCHIMIA in industrial use-cases. V2 – Due: M27 MS12.- Integration and validation of ALCHIMIA in industrial use-cases. Final – Due: M36		

3.3.6 WP6: Exploitation, dissemination and environmental impact

Table 34: WP6: General Information

Lead Beneficiary	MI		
WP Leader	Anna Brékiné		
Start Month	M1	End Month	M36

3.3.6.1 Task 6.1: Strategy for Impact Creation and Content

Table 35: T6.1: General Information

Lead Beneficiary	MI		
Task Leader	Anna Brékiné		
Start Month	M1	End Month	M36
Deliverables produced by the task	D6.1 - Plan for impact creation, standardisation and exploitation' – Due: M6		
Related Milestones	MS3.- ALCHIMIA outreach and standardisation plan – Due: M6		

3.3.6.2 Task 6.2: Standardisation

Table 36: T6.2: General Information

Lead Beneficiary	BFI		
Task Leader	Waldemar Krieger		
Start Month	M1	End Month	M36
Deliverables produced by the task	D6.1 - Plan for impact creation, standardisation and exploitation – Due: M6		
Related Milestones	MS3.- ALCHIMIA outreach and standardisation plan – Due: M6		

3.3.6.3 Task 6.3: Environmental Impact Assessment

Table 37: T6.3: General Information

Lead Beneficiary	MI		
Task Leader	Anna Bréchine		
Start Month	M12	End Month	M36
Deliverables produced by the task	D6.3 - Environmental Impact Assessment – Due: M36		
Related Milestones	MS7.- Preliminary environmental impact assessment – Due: M18		

3.3.6.4 Task 6.4: Business Exploitation and Sustainability

Table 38: T6.4: General Information

Lead Beneficiary	MI		
Task Leader	Anna Bréline		
Start Month	M1	End Month	M36
Deliverables produced by the task	D6.2 - 'D6.2 Final Report on impact creation, standardisation and exploitation – Due: M36		
Related Milestones	MS8.- IPR management and business models – Due: M22 MS13.- ALCHIMIA exploitation agreement – Due: M36		

4 Project Management

4.1 Project Governance

The project governance is the management framework defining how the project decisions must be taken. Its structure indicates specific project players, their roles and responsibilities, as well as their interaction way for the life of the project. This structure aims at an effective project evaluation, control, and decision-taking, while ensuring an effective participation, motivation of all partners, and a proper conflict resolution.

4.1.1 Management Structure and Procedures

The overall management structure is presented in the following figure:

Figure 2 – ALCHIMIA Management Structure

The following table presents each role with its belonging members:

Table 39: Partners roles

Role/Group	Partners
General Assembly (GA)	One representative per beneficiary
Steering Committee (SC)	ATOS, BFI, MI, SSSA, CAR, CEL
Project Coordinator (PC)	ATOS
Technical Coordinator (TC)	BFI
Exploitation Manager (EM)	MI
Quality Manager (QM)	ATOS
Ethics Manager (EtM)	SSSA
Work Package Leaders (WPL)	ATOS, CAR, SSSA, CEL MI
Tasks Leaders (TL)	ATOS, SSSA, CEL, CAR, EXUS, BFI, FDT, MI

4.1.2 Decision making process

There are a number of ways the consortium can arrive at a decision, frequently due to trade-offs of time-cost-quality, or around the emergence of a risk.

Figure 3 – Decision making process

The decision-making process comprises four steps, as indicated in the figure above:

- Identification of the decision. This step determines that a decision is needed and requires identifying alternatives or possible paths of action and gathering relevant information or provisions to support the analysis step, such as associated risks, costs implications, scope or quality implications, or even regulatory and contractual provisions.
- Analysis of the decision. Based on the available information, the decision team evaluates and discuss the alternatives and make a decision.
- Render the decision. This phase implements the agreed actions.
- Decision tracking. During this phase the decision team assesses how well the selected actions delivered the desired (or expected) positive outcomes.

Communication: All the previous steps are supported by the communication process, so that information is spread throughout all the decision-making groups and project organizations.

The basic approach for the decision-making process is to locate the decision as close as possible to the level responsible for the execution (from task level to GA level). Effort for discussion and decision-making shall be kept at the lowest necessary level.

Decisions are managed within project meetings (described in Meetings and Procedures), either on-site or teleconference. Decisions can be also managed by consultation. If voting is needed, the agenda should clearly indicate this fact. Quorum and voting rules will be defined in the Consortium Agreement. Decisions are binding once the relevant part of the meeting minutes has been accepted.

Decisions are also expected to happen around the project milestones, as defined with control points in the project Overall Work Plan.

Any changes to the project plan and scope must be reviewed and approved by all levels of project management, before proposing these changes to the Project Coordination Team and any modification will be considered rejected, after rejection on any of these involved levels.

4.1.3 Conflict resolution

One of the goals of the consortium is to avoid any unnecessary conflicts. Nevertheless, should they arise, a conflict resolution and escalation process will be ready to be put in place to deal with them accordingly. The conflict resolution and escalation process require each conflict to be intermediated, solved or decided at the lowest level possible. Attempts to solve issues within the consortium will be carried out in increasing order of authority by means of dialogue and mutual concession, first at Task level (management of TL), WP level (management of WPL), and then following the management bodies till the General Assembly (GA). Further rules related to conflict resolutions will be laid out in the Consortium Agreement.

If necessary, the Project Coordination Team will organise a conflict resolution meeting within fifteen (15) calendar days following the reception of a written request transmitted by any partner or body of the project. Attempts of arbitration will be performed in increasing order of authority:

- Within the team of each work package under the management of the work package leader.

- Within the Project Coordination Team.

4.2 Project Communication

The internal communication goal is to ensure that all consortium members and working groups within the project have access to all the information they require to make informed decisions and capitalize on their output. A good internal communication is an important asset to achieve the project expectations and objectives.

The internal communication seeks the following objectives:

- All consortium members are aware of the project's vision and objectives.
- All project decisions are communicated effectively to consortium members.
- All consortium members understand and know how to follow all policies and procedures related to their participation in the project.
- All consortium members are familiar with the resources available in, and the updates and developments of programmes other than their own.
- All consortium members are able to provide feedback to management through formal channels.

Communication is managed by implementing some rules, concerning in particular:

- Organisation of official meetings (General Assembly, Project Coordination Team, etc.)
- Rules for meetings organisation, according to the needs of the project, and requiring a pre-agenda and meeting minutes, for comments and approval of the attendees.
- Rules at providing and maintaining information at all project levels.
- Information sharing by means of an electronic repository accessible to the consortium members.
- Project mailing lists.
- The use of standard documents templates to ensure uniformity of information and identification of the documents.

4.2.1 Contact lists

Contact list is available for all project consortium members in the project repository, in the following link:

<https://newrepository.atosresearch.eu/index.php/apps/files?dir=/ALCHIMIA/Management/Contact%20lists>

4.2.2 Email and emailing lists

Mailing lists are the principal mean of interpersonal communication in the project. The objectives of the mailing lists are to provide an easy and fast way to communicate to the project members, keeping track record of communication and archives of the information exchanged. Appropriate uses of mailing lists include scheduling meetings, forwarding documents or other information, and general questions and answers.

4.2.2.1 Use of mailing lists

The project has set-up the following mailing lists:

Table 40: ALCHIMIA mailing lists

Name	Address	Purpose
General	alchimia@lists.atosresearch.eu	For general related purposes; all people involved in the project is subscribed to this mailing list
Management	alchimia-mgmt@lists.atosresearch.eu	For management related purposes
WP2	alchimia_wp2@lists.atosresearch.eu	For WP2 related purposes
WP3	alchimia_wp3@lists.atosresearch.eu	For WP3 related purposes
WP4	alchimia_wp4@lists.atosresearch.eu	For WP4 related purposes
WP5	alchimia_wp5@lists.atosresearch.eu	For WP5 related purposes
WP6	alchimia_wp6@lists.atosresearch.eu	For WP6 related purposes

4.2.2.2 Management

The mailing lists are hosted and managed by ATOS, responsible for the project communication infrastructure. These lists are based on Mailman, free software for managing electronic mail discussion, and distributed under the GNU General Public License. Mailman supports built-in archiving, automatic bounce processing, content filtering, digest delivery, and spam filters.

The management of the mailing lists are the ultimate responsibility of ATOS as coordinator. Nonetheless, every partner is accountable to notify the coordination team about any change in the list: inclusion of new members, modification of existing details, or the removal of included names.

Each user can edit its membership information, subscription, passwords and options from a web interface of the mailing list. The access to this interface is provided in the "Welcome" message at the time of the subscription.

4.2.2.3 Communication rules

For a suitable use of the mailing lists, these rules are to be followed by all partners:

- SUBJECT:
 - Make sure to add the "ALCHIMIA" word in front of the subject line, to identify the communication. E-mails addresses to the official mailing lists will automatically have an identifier appended in front of the subject line, like [alchimial].
 - To segment the information, include the corresponding WP in the subject, followed by the real subject.
 - Use explicit subject title. The subject should be a clear indication of the content (for instance, "WP1", "Meeting minutes 2019-01-28").
 - Responses to the email should keep the topic.
- It is highly recommended to keep record of the conclusions and decided actions of the email.
- It is highly advisable to consider if the decided actions should trigger other project mechanisms, such as: i) add other partners/roles in the loop, ii) ask for support, advice, or arbitration, iii) raise any potential risk to the pertinent role or consortium body.
- ATTACHMENTS. Try to avoid attachments as much as possible in your emails, using a link to the repository instead.

4.2.3 Conferencing system

ATOS provides its teleconference tool, Microsoft Teams¹. To assure a proper communication process, periodic teleconference meetings should be scheduled on regular basis. For the SC, TC and WP at least one conference per month is recommendable. And always the conferences can be arranged on demand, if necessary.

The agenda for the teleconferences should be provided by the conference chair at least seven days before the meeting. The minutes of the conference should be elaborated and circulated to all participants by the conference leader. The conference leader will be also in charge of uploading the minutes to the repository.

¹ <https://www.microsoft.com/es-es/microsoft-teams/group-chat-software>

4.2.4 Project repository

All project-related documentation will be stored in the project repository. It provides the support needed by the documentation storage, review process, information sharing, and work in groups by all partners in order to achieve the common goals of the project.

All relevant information for the project is to be stored in this repository, including contractual documents (GA, CA), amendments, review-related documentation, reporting documentation, contact details, templates, working documents of deliverables, internal working documents, agendas, minutes, etc. Moreover, final versions of all deliverables are to be uploaded there.

The project repository is based on OWN CLOUD² and is hosted by ATOS. ATOS will provide all partners with their access credentials.

4.2.4.1 Structure

The project repository is available from the following URL: <https://repository.atosresearch.eu/repository>

This repository is initially organized by work packages of the project. Each folder will contain a subfolder structure, containing the WP meetings and one subfolder per deliverable. Other required folders are possible, always with a descriptive name of the content. Current repository structure is shown in capture below:

Figure 4 – ALCHIMIA repository structure

4.2.4.2 Management and maintenance

ATOS is responsible for the general maintenance of this project repository. Work Package leaders are in charge of the documents organisation related to their WP. Deliverable

² <https://owncloud.com/>

editors are responsible for keeping updated versions of the corresponding deliverable. All partners are responsible for supporting the documentation management process.

4.2.4.3 Technology

The project repository is based on OwnCloud version 8.0. OwnCloud is a suite of client-server software for creating file hosting services and using them.

The OwnCloud server is written in the PHP and JavaScript scripting languages. For remote access, it employs sabre/dav, an open-source WebDAV server. OwnCloud is designed to work with several database management systems, for example MySQL.

4.2.4.4 Information security

With regards to the security procedure, the project repository is subject to the ATOS Information Security Policy, aiming at safeguarding the confidentiality, integrity, availability, authenticity and non-repudiation of information and information systems. It is based on an internationally accepted security standard (ISO27002 -, Code of Practice for Information Security Management³).

The policy applies to all intellectual and physical forms of information assets, whether owned, used or held in custody by ATOS. This policy is mandatory for the security of ATOS internal and external business processes and applies to all staff, contractors and consultants throughout the ATOS organization.

4.2.4.5 Data Management Plan

The data management plan is defined in the deliverable D1.2 Data Management Plan, expected by month M6 of the project (February 2023).

4.2.5 Meetings and procedures

Meetings are used to report and certify the status of the project or the work packages, debating special project issues, as well as for decision making. E-mail and teleconferences shall be used as main options for solving issues on an operative day-to-day basis.

4.2.5.1 Rules for meeting organisation

The rules for the implementation of meetings must be the following:

- A meeting notice shall be issued in proper advance with respect to the event, in order to allow participants to manage the preparation and if it is necessary logistic issues. For physical meetings, the agenda and meeting notice should be sent at least with twenty-one (21) calendar days preceding the meeting. For virtual meetings, the agenda and meeting notice should be sent at least seven (7) calendar days before the meeting.

³ International Organization for Standardization. "ISO/IEC 27002:2013 Information technology — Security techniques — Code of practice for information security controls". <http://www.iso27001security.com/html/27002.html>, retrieved on 29-01-2015.

- Modality (face to face meetings or conference call), duration and venue of the meetings shall be proposed by the convener and communicated in advance. Dates and locations need to be agreed by the meeting chair and participants in advance to leverage the team availability and to reduce travel costs.
- The notice shall include a draft agenda of items to be discussed, giving an overview of any proposed decision. Upon agreement among the participants, decisions can be made in relation to any matter not mentioned in the agenda.
- Minutes of the meeting shall be produced by the chairperson of the meeting (PC, TC, WP leaders or task leaders depending on the meeting level) and transmitted to the attendees not later than ten (10) calendar days after the meeting. The minutes shall be considered as accepted, if within ten (10) calendar days there are no objections in a written form. The minutes must at least should contain:
 - The attendance list of the meeting.
 - The agenda.
 - Decisions taken and an action list containing a responsible and deadline for each action.
- Minutes must be suitable stored by the chairperson in the project repository.

The periods specified in this section could be adjusted if unanimously agreed by all members of the given body.

4.2.5.2 Meeting roles

There are three roles to consider:

- The meeting chair is the person/role in charge of steering the meeting.
 - The Project Coordinator is the chair of the General Assembly and the Steering Committee.
 - The WP leader is the chair of the subproject meetings at WP level.
 - The Task leader is the chair of the subproject meetings at task level.
- The host is the organization in charge of dealing with the face-to-face meeting preparations, supporting locally the meeting chair. This includes reserving a suitable room for the expected number of attendees, with the necessary equipment, and providing the participants with logistic and accommodation information. The host role is expected to rotate during the project lifetime.
- Participant is any stakeholder that takes part in the meeting. Participants will follow the host's instructions with regard to the requirements to attend the meeting (for example, security policies).

4.2.5.3 General assembly meetings

The general assembly meetings must be chaired by the project coordinator and should cover all major issues (technical and non-technical) where a position of the consortium is expected. The project coordinator will only summon dedicated general assembly meetings in case this is considered necessary. A consortium partner can send more than one representative to a general assembly meeting but multiple delegates of a consortium partner vote on behalf of their organisation according to the rules defined by the consortium.

The general assembly will meet at least twice per year being one of those meetings physical and if possible, combined with other project meetings in order to limit travelling costs to partners.

4.2.5.4 Steering committee meetings

The steering committee meetings must be chaired by the project coordinator. These meetings should be used to exchange technical information, prepare semi-annual reporting and reviews, and report the project progress. One part of the meeting should be dedicated to the general assembly where major decisions on technical and non-technical issues are taken.

The steering committee will meet at least twice per year, and at least one of them must be physical (combined with other project meetings). For the steering committee there will be a monthly teleconference on the first Wednesday of every month at 11:00 CET.

4.2.5.5 Subproject meetings

Subproject meetings are usually technical meetings including the work package leader, task leaders, deliverable editors and any other partner required in the related topic of the meeting.

The frequency of the meetings is decided by the work package leader, but it is advisable to celebrate a meeting at least once per month, preferably via conference call.

In case of a monthly call the agenda should be sent at least one week in advance and the minutes of the meeting should be produced within 10 days after the meeting.

WP meetings are chaired by WPLs. Additional technical meetings may be set up by TLs or individual partners after informing the WPL. All meetings will be documented by minutes listing major decisions and action items. Meeting agendas, individual to-do lists and other important project information will be accessible via the collaboration platform, to allow for remote teamwork.

4.2.5.6 Meeting calendar

All meetings agreed should be registered in the project meetings calendar. Each chairperson (PC, TC, or WP leaders depending on the meeting level) is responsible to inform the consortium of all meetings (teleconference or physical meetings) to take place in the next months and also to register in the project meetings calendar.

4.3 Project monitoring

The main goal of this process is to oversee all the tasks and metrics needed to ensure that the project is within scope, on time and also on budget. The project Coordinator is in charge of this process, with the support of the Technical Coordinator.

The monitoring will be performed against the project work plan, described in the project DoA and also on the section Overall Work Plan of this deliverable, in which are stated the objectives of the project, its Work Breakdown Structure (Scope), the project roadmap (time) and the budget allocated for all Work Packages.

The following key performance indicators (KPI) were defined in order to control the project execution against the three main project restraints (scope, time, budget). The evolution of the level of achievement of these KPIs will be reported through the periodic reports.

Table 41: Project management KPIs

KPI	Purpose
Deviation of planned cost (%)	To monitor and control cost consumption against plan
Deviation of planned effort (PM) (%)	To monitor and control effort consumption against plan
Number of milestones missed	To monitor and control ability to meet schedule
Number of late deliverables	To monitor and control ability to meet schedule. This parameter can be identified by WPL.
The number of days the review of a deliverable is late	To monitor and control the degree of lateness
Number of days to review a deliverable	To monitor and control ability to meet schedule
Number of meetings	To monitor and control internal communication and decisions. This indicator can be split into the different WPs.
Number of raised disputes	To monitor and control internal conflict
Number of unresolved issues	To monitor and control internal conflict and consortium ability to resolve them

4.4 Technical monitoring

The main goal of this process is to oversee all the tasks and metrics needed to ensure that the technical goals of the project are being achieved. The technical coordinator is in charge of this process, with the support of the project coordinator.

The technical monitoring will be performed against the project technical goals described in the section 1 of the DoA and also against the KPI table created by each WP Leader using as template the table presented in this sub-section.

The evolution of this KPIs will be reported through the periodic reports as well.

4.4.1 Technical KPIs table

To assemble and measure progress made by the different WPs, a template for the technical progress monitoring was designed and delivered to the WP Leaders (see Table 42: ALCHIMIA Technical Management KPIs template).

The template supports the technical progress monitoring as part of the ALCHIMIA Quality Plan and will be completed by each WP Leader with the support of the respective Task Leaders.

Each WPs defines (operational) goals complemented with (quantified when possible) measures for measuring the progress towards technical goals realization, which is to be understood as a measurement of the progress towards the achievements and, when applicable, corrective actions taken.

This technical monitoring template will be first completed at the beginning of the project and then reviewed in the SC meetings. It will be reported to the E.C. at the end of every reporting period.

4.4.2 How to fill the table

The columns Objectives of the WP and Measures should be completed with the knowledge the consortium has at M1 of project lifetime.

At the end of each internal reporting period, two more columns will be added for the purpose of the control and monitoring (Status and Corrective actions), see section Internal Interim Activity Reports (IAR).

Also, a % should be provided in order the consortium can have a clear picture of the progress in relation with the total.

An indication on how to fill each column is given as follows:

- Objectives of the WP: Provide the WP objectives as per DoA. If the WP Leader wishes to refine the goals, as long they do not deviate from the DoA and leave the goal clearer, it is allowed to do so.
- Measures (quantified – not generic): Define how the success towards the defined objectives will be measured, if possible, by using quantified measures. The measures ought to be clear and not leave room for interpretation of what is expected.

The Quality Manager will ensure that each WP will define a set of Technical KPIs at the beginning of the project and reviewed and evaluated at end of each internal reporting period. In case no new KPIs arise, at least the update of the previously identified KPIs is mandatory.

Table 42: ALCHIMIA Technical Management KPIs template

WP N°:	WPx	WP Title	WPx - xxxxxx		
	Objectives of the WP		Measures (quantified – not generic)		
1.	i.e. PILOTS demonstrating the new functionalities		5 pilots at M30 ready to show		
2.					
3.					
Start Month	Mxx	End Month	Mxx	Overall Progress of the WP (%)	Xxx %

4.5 Contractual management

The objective of the contractual management is to ensure that the project is adhering to the terms and conditions of the Grant Agreement (the contract with the European Commission) and providing the required services/products that meet the expectations of the project.

In particular, the contract management addresses the following situations:

- Changes in the consortium configuration, such as including addition or withdrawal of beneficiaries or third parties.
- Changes in the technical scope of the project, affecting the Description of Action.
- Changes in the Consortium Agreement.
- Contract closing.

Contractual changes are decided at the General Assembly in accordance to the procedures set out within the CA and the article 55 of the Grant Agreement (except in the case of change of coordinator). The Steering Committee can also propose changes to the General Assembly. Any changes to the project plan and scope must be reviewed and approved by all levels of project management, before proposing these changes to the GA, and any modification will be considered rejected, after rejection on any of these involved levels.

The project coordinator is in charge of processing and coordinating any amendment on behalf of the consortium. The project coordinator is also responsible for transferring any contractual change to the project plan.

4.6 Administrative and Financial reporting

4.6.1 Reporting to the EC

The beneficiaries must provide reports to request payments, in accordance with the schedule and modalities set out in the Data Sheet:

- for additional prefinancings (if any): an additional prefinancing report
- for interim payments (if any) and the final payment: a periodic report.

The prefinancing and periodic reports include a technical and financial part. The technical part includes an overview of the action implementation. It must be prepared using the template available in the Portal Periodic Reporting tool.

The financial part of the additional prefinancing report includes a statement on the use of the previous prefinancing payment.

The financial part of the periodic report includes:

- the financial statements (individual and consolidated; for all beneficiaries/affiliated entities)
- the explanation on the use of resources (or detailed cost reporting table, if required)

- the certificates on the financial statements (CFS) (if required, see Article 24.2 and Data Sheet, Point 4.3).

The financial statements must detail the eligible costs and contributions for each budget category and, for the final payment, also the revenues for the action (see Articles 6 and 22).

All eligible costs and contributions incurred should be declared, even if they exceed the amounts indicated in the estimated budget. Amounts that are not declared in the individual financial statements will not be taken into account by the granting authority.

By signing the financial statements (directly in the Portal Periodic Reporting tool), the beneficiaries confirm that:

- the information provided is complete, reliable and true
- the costs and contributions declared are eligible (see Article 6)
- the costs and contributions can be substantiated by adequate records and supporting documents (see Article 20) that will be produced upon request (see Article 19) or in the context of checks, reviews, audits and investigations (see Article 25)
- for the final periodic report: all the revenues have been declared (if required; see Article 22).

Beneficiaries will have to also submit the financial statements of their affiliated entities (if any). In case of recoveries (see Article 22), beneficiaries will be held responsible also for the financial statements of their affiliated entities.

4.6.2 Internal Interim Activity Reports (IAR)

According to the CA internal controls will be periodically done in order to assure the proper development of the project, both in terms of activity and use of resources. These reports are intended for internal use, therefore, they won't be delivered to the EC.

To that end, an internal interim activity report (IAR) will be carried out at the end of every six months. These IARs will include reports on partners' activity in each active work package.

Each report should inform about:

- Main activities and main achievements in last six months.
- A summary of the resources (efforts) consumed in each WP during the considered tranche.

These reports would be cumulative, so the information provided in a given period should be updated in the next periods. These reports will also be used to feed into the periodic reports for the EC.

The PC will compile all inputs and generate reports per WP that will be verified with the WP leaders. This control action will help understand the project situation (by comparing with the work plans) and apply corrective measures when necessary.

The information received within this internal reporting will be used by the PC as input for the production of a periodical report on the progress of the project to the entire consortium.

ATOS, as coordinator, has prepared two different templates to be compulsorily used by all the partners.

- ALCHIMIA_IAR_Template: Interim Activity report
- ALCHIMIA_FPR_Template: Financial Project Report

Figure 5 – Reporting flow

How do we produce the report?

- Timeline: Producing the report takes 2 months, from the request for contributions to the final delivery. Interim reports are produced at the end of every six-months. As an example, for period M1-M6 the report should be ready by the end of M7. Same logic applies for the rest of periods.
- The Project Coordinator provides the templates and request contributions 30 days in advance of the deadline for providing inputs (e.g: end M5 for the first report).
- WP leaders coordinate with partners and provide a summary of the activities and main achievements for the WP.
- All partners provide their efforts in the provided template.
- The Project Coordinator collects reports, produce an integrated draft version and delivery it to WPs leaders' approval of activity and partners' PM declaration.
- The Project Coordinator integrates the WP leaders' inputs, review them, and produce a final version.

Table 43: Example of timeline reporting

	M5	M6	M7
IAR1	PC requests inputs covering M1-M6	Partners contributions in terms of PM	15 days after deadline: PC Draft Version
		WP contributions in terms of Activity	By the end of the month: PC Final Version

Within this project, the IARs will be produced according to this schedule:

Table 44: IARs schedule

	Period	Request Inputs	Contributions	Final version
IAR1	M1-M6	M5	M6	M7
IAR2	M7-M12	M11	M12	M13
IAR3	M19-M24	M23	M24	M25
IAR4	M25-M30	M29	M30	M31

4.6.3 Financial reporting

The financial reporting consists of structured forms (called "Financial Statements") from the grant management system. Horizon Europe offers an online manual containing all the information relevant for the project execution at administrative and financial level, and specifically all the information related to financial issues, personnel costs calculation and costs' eligibility. It can be accessed here:

<https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/funding-tenders-opportunities/display/OM/Online+Manual>

4.6.4 Budget & payments

The project coordinator receives from the EC the funds aimed at covering the grant amount to all partners for the performance of the project tasks as stated in the Grant Agreement (GA).

According to the GA Art. 5.1, the maximum financial contribution of the European Commission to the project is 2,576,987.50 €. From this amount, the consortium received at the beginning of the project a prefinancing payment of 1,932,740.62 € that are distributed according to the payment scheme agreed in the CA (Article 7.2).

The project coordinator shall keep project funds in a bank account and will keep records of the balance of available project funds (called "Spot Balance") at all times. The Spot Balance shall be determined every day incremented by any transfer from the EC received by the project coordinator with respect of any partner or with funds recovered by the project coordinator from any partner and decremented by the transfers made by the project coordinator to any partner.

In particular, the following concepts are relevant to the spot balance:

- Bank Balance: Actual status of the bank funds on the project coordinator side.
- Payment: Represents the amounts transfer from the EC to the project coordinator.
- Payment accumulated: Accumulative amount of funds transferred from the project coordinator to partners.

5 Quality assurance

The following section describes the mechanisms that will be used throughout the project in order to ensure the quality level of project outcomes, especially the contractual deliverables.

5.1 Document management process

5.1.1 Documents language

English is the official language in Horizon Europe projects; therefore, all the documents must be written in British English, using the appropriate grammar rules and a formal language. Some dissemination material (such as press releases, newsletters, fliers, etc.) can be considered as an exception for this rule and can be translated to other relevant languages for the project.

5.1.2 Documents storage

The project must provide methods for information sharing by using a project electronic repository, accessible to the consortium members, where all the common project information and shareable information will be stored and updated.

A partner within the consortium should be assigned as responsible for the general maintenance of the project repository. Work package leaders are responsible for the document organization of their corresponding work package. Deliverable leaders are responsible of the maintenance of their documents. All partners contributing to a document are responsible of the maintenance of the document according to the guidelines included in this document and the instructions given by the deliverable leader.

The internal structure for the electronic repository can be chosen by the consortium in the best way fitting the project purposes but it should be clear and comprehensible by all partners and designed in a way aiming to facilitate the internal work. It is advisable to name the root folder using the short name of the project and include the following folders (including a sub-folder structure where needed):

- **Management:** This folder should contain all the administrative documentation such as Consortium Agreement, Grant Agreement, project amendments (if any), project budget, project time-plan, etc. Different subfolders will also include all support documentation used in the project, including templates, contacts, and reference material.
- **Deliverables submitted:** This folder should contain the deliverables final version sent to the EC (in PDF format).
- **Meetings:** all support documentation related to project meetings.
- **Work Packages:** This folder should contain all the working versions for the project deliverables and documents, organised in a work package manner, so it should contain at least a sub-folder for each of the work packages of the project. The work package folder organisation is responsibility of the work package leader, but it is advisable to include a sub-folder for each of the work package's tasks.

5.1.3 Documents nomenclature

The deliverable leader should name all the deliverables of the project previous to the final version according to the following nomenclature:

Project_Dx.y_Name_vm.n_[suffix]

Where:

- Project: project short name.
- Dx.y: is the deliverable number as defined in the DoA, being x the number of the work package and y the deliverable number within the work package.
- Name: The name should match exactly with the name for the deliverable as defined in the DoA.
- vm.nn:
 - m: 0 for the draft versions, 1 for the final version (delivered to the EC).
 - n: consecutive number from 0 to 9. Can be extended to several digits if necessary.
- Suffix (optional): can be used to identify intermediate versions or contributions from partners to a draft version (never in a final version) and could include dates, short name of partners, etc.

5.1.4 Bibliographical references

An example of how the bibliographical references must be made can be found in the references section of this document and the deliverable template.

5.1.5 Documents templates

Project documents should be based in the following templates, which should be available in the project electronic repository:

- MxxMeeting_yyyymmdd_ALCHIMIA_agenda-minutes_template_v2.0: Agenda/Minutes template in MS Word.
- ALCHIMIA_List_of_participants_template.docx: List of participants in MS Word.
- ALCHIMIA_Dxy_Deliverable_template.docx: Deliverable template in MS Word.
- ALCHIMIA_Powerpoint_template.pptx: Presentation template in MS Power Point.
- ALCHIMIA_Peer_review_evaluation_template.docx: Deliverable Review Form in MS Word.

Other templates can be produced if necessary.

5.2 Quality guidelines on deliverables production

All deliverables content provided by ALCHIMIA should follow these guidelines [4][5]:

5.2.1 Legibility

- When writing, stick to the format provided by the template of your project, respecting fonts, sizes and styles for each text level, line spaces, indent style, margins, and layout.
- Respect the graphical identity of this project.
- The widespread use of capitals is not recommended.
- Consideration should be given to using different heading levels to enable key information to stand out and to facilitate navigation in the text.
- Avoid clutter. Keep a neat, clean and professional text appearance.
- When referring to other parts of the text, cross-references should be added (instead of regular text). It ensures always referencing the right bookmark in cases of moving the text block to other position of changes in the ToC.
- Ensure there are no broken links after finalizing the writing, by searching "Error" through the whole document.
- Deliverable leaders: at the moment to produce the final pdf, check text legibility and positioning of pictures by quick scanning it. In some occasions the pictures could be moved.
- Do not use links in the text, use references instead.

5.2.2 Readability

- Long sentences should be avoided. It is better to use a couple of sentences rather than one longer, complicated sentence, especially for new information. Especially avoid compound sentences with many subordinate clauses and conjunctions.
- Long paragraphs can confuse readers. Chunking text can help solve this problem. By adding necessary white space for improved text scanability and readability, while paragraphs give structure to your written work.
- Use connectives to unify your writing between and within paragraph. Examples of connectives: "Nonetheless," "Besides," "However," "Furthermore," and "Alternatively".
- Abbreviations and acronyms should be avoided in general unless these are appropriate. When first used in the text, the meaning should be spelled out in full.
- Mainly write in the active voice.
- Use text levels to separate the content.
- Use short sub-headlines.

- Use bullet points and numbered lists to catch attention, create structure content, and help reader in the consumption of information. But where possible, no more than five or six bullet points in a list are recommended.
- Avoid text wraps. Wrapping text around figures, blocks, or other elements can cause text to break inelegantly. This disturbs a reader's rhythmic eye movement and interferes with an individual's scanning speed. For the same reason, do not justify text in tables.
- Time references
 - Do not use relative time references (i.e. next month, last year)
 - Use only absolute time references (i.e. June 2017, M24)
 - Always refer to month including the year as well

5.2.3 Comprehension

- Use terms familiar to the audience of our deliverables in order to ease content comprehension.
- Use an "inverted-pyramid writing style"[3], starting with the conclusion or an overview of the main point.
- Pictures and diagrams can sometimes explain things better than large amounts of words.
- Start with a table of contents to be discussed and agreed by all required contributors.
- Ensure that all sections relate to the main goal of the document and among themselves.
- Keep the document short, concise and to the point.
- Avoid unnecessary texts as repetitions from other deliverables from this project, instead just add a reference to them (i.e. for further information please refer to ALCHIMIA_Dx.x - xxxx)

5.3 Deliverables review

5.3.1 Internal review planning

The deliverable review process is initiated by the project Quality Manager. The first step is the creation of the internal review planning document.

The document lists all the project deliverables and appoints two organizations as peer reviewers for the deliverable based, if possible, in the following criteria:

- The number of deliverables assigned to an organization should be proportional to the workload of the organization within the project.

- The organizations in charge of the deliverable review should not be directly involved in the specific task and deliverable but having enough knowledge of the area in which the deliverable was based.
- The persons within the organization reviewing the document should have at least basic knowledge about the project, ideally being persons working in the project but not involved in the development of the task and deliverable.

5.3.2 Roles and responsibilities

The roles and responsibilities of the deliverable review process can be seen in the following table:

Table 45: Roles and responsibilities on Deliverable Review

Role	Responsibilities
Project Coordinator (PC)	<p>Evaluation of the final version of the document after the deliverable review process.</p> <p>Formal approval of the version to be sent to the European Commission (EC).</p>
Quality Manager (QM)	<p>Supervision of the deliverable review process from start to end, establishing the review process dates.</p> <p>Support the peer reviewers and DT during the deliverable review process.</p> <p>Perform a final format review and produce the final version to be sent to the PC for the formal approval and release to the EC.</p>
Technical Coordinator (TC)	<p>Support the DT with advice if required, in order the DT can proper address the PR comments.</p> <p>Reads the Table of Contents and check if the technical content is aligned with the general objectives of the project</p>
Deliverable Leader (DL)	<p>Lead the deliverable team during the development of the deliverable.</p> <p>Contact the persons reviewing the deliverable and coordinating the review team during the process.</p> <p>Process the evaluation form sent by the PR and address the changes needed in the deliverable.</p> <p>Send the final version for the QM for format revision.</p>
Deliverable Team (DT)	<p>Produce and contribute to the draft version following the DL instructions.</p> <p>Support the DL addressing the changes needed in the deliverable.</p>

Role	Responsibilities
Peer reviewer (PR)	Evaluate the content and format of the deliverable using the peer review evaluation template. Can require assistance from the TC in case of doubts.

5.3.3 Deliverable review process

The deliverable review process is designed to improve the quality of the project outputs and minimise the risk of rejections.

The deliverable review process is represented graphically in the following figure:

Figure 6 – Deliverable review process

As previous steps to the deliverable review process, the DT and the DL must create a draft following the next (informal) steps:

Table 46: Review process main process

Step	Responsible	Description
S1	DL	Nominates and contacts the production team (contributors). Set up the structure of the deliverable, based in the deliverable template.
S2	TC	Reads the Table of Contents and check if the technical content is aligned with the general objectives of the project
S3	DL	Coordinates the production of the deliverable. Sends the draft to the WPL for the first check.
S4	WPL	Oversees the production of the deliverable according with the objectives of the WP
S5	DL	Address the changes suggested by the WPL (if any) and creates the candidate draft to be sent to the deliverable review process.

During all this process the project electronic repository must be used in order to exchange documents.

Once the final draft is ready, the deliverable review process is initiated. The deliverable review process should be initiated at least one month before the official submission date so the reviewers have time to evaluate the deliverable and the deliverable leader and the deliverable team have time to integrate the input from the Review Form.

The following table shows the steps of the process along with the estimation (in working days) for each step:

Table 47: Review process steps

Step	Responsible	Description	Duration
R0	QM	Set-up a calendar for the deliverable review process. Informs the interested people (DL, TC, PR and WPL) providing advice about the procedures and dates.	0
R1	DL	Contact the peer reviewers with instructions about the evaluation (QM must be in Cc). Sends the candidate draft to the previously assigned per reviewers in order to initiate the deliverable review process.	0
R2	PR	PRs review the final draft using the Review Form (Annex IV. Peer Review Form), including an evaluation of each of the listed categories and recommendations for refinement if necessary. The PRs can also send a commented/edited version of the draft.	4

Step	Responsible	Description	Duration
R3	DL	<p>According to the PRs decision:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fill the proper field in the deliverable's quality control table and send the final deliverable to the QM. • If necessary, reactivates the DT in order to implement the comments included in the Review Form and send the new draft to the PR, accompanied by a report about the implementation of the changes (text in the email body is accepted). • If necessary, consult the WPL and/or TC for further advice, giving them one working day to reply. 	4
R4	QM	Receive the inputs from the DL (revised draft, peer review reports), decide and communicate the next action: publication (see RF1 below) or format refinement (see R5 below).	2
R5	QM	<p>In case of format refinement, the QM will implement minor format changes and if needed ask the DL to perform major format changes.</p> <p>Once the format is accepted by the QM, the next action publication takes place (see RF1 below).</p>	1
RF1	QM	Fill the deliverable's quality control table with DL and QM checks and send it to the PC for the final approval and release to the EC.	1
RF2	PC	<p>Reviews the final version of the document.</p> <p>Although it should not happen, the PC could ask for changes in the deliverable. In this case, the DL will set-up a calendar, including any steps from R1 to R5 above, remaining anyways within the maximum duration of the deliverable review process.</p> <p>Convert the file to PDF and deliver it to the EC services.</p>	1

During the deliverable review process, the project electronic repository must be used in order to exchange documents.

5.3.4 Deliverable review process responsibility matrix

The following responsibility assignment matrix (RAM) summarises the roles and responsibilities within the deliverable review process, according to a RASCI model (for more information please see section 9.1.2.1 of [1]):

Table 48: Review process responsibility matrix

Task	PC	QM	TC	WPL	DL	DT	PR
Deliverable draft creation		C	C	A	R	S	
Deliverable review process initiation and set-up		R	I	I	I	I	I
Deliverable changes		C/S	I	A	R	S	
Deliverable draft approval	I	I	S	I	I	I	R
Deliverable format approval	I	R	S	I	S	I	
Deliverable formal approval and release to the EC	R	I	I	I	I		

- Responsible (R): that is the role who is owner of the task.
- Accountable (A): that is the role to which "R" is Accountable and is the authority who approves to sign off on work before it is effective.
- Supportive (S): that is a role that provides resources or plays a supporting role in implementation of the task.
- Consulted (C): that is a role that provides information and/or expertise necessary to complete the task.
- Informed (I): that is a role that needs to be notified of results but need not necessarily be consulted.
- Blank: no involvement necessary.

6 Risk management

The risk management process is vital for any project in order to anticipate situations that can affect the normal progress or even put in danger the continuation of the project. This anticipation will provide the ALCHIMIA consortium with enough information to take decisions accordingly and act beforehand to minimise the impact of the risks identified.

The Risk Management methodology presented in this guide follows the PMI (Project Management Institute) guidelines as presented in the PMBOK® Guide [1]

6.1 Risk Management Processes

Risk management will be implemented in ALCHIMIA through five processes, in a continuous improvement approach during the project lifetime:

- Plan Risk Management
- Identify Risks
- Risk Analysis
- Plan Risk responses
- Control Risks

Figure 7 – Risk Management processes cycle

6.2 Plan Risk Management

As depicted in the figure above, the first process to take place is the Plan Risk Management.

At this stage, all the following processes needed for the proper risk management process of the project are designed. Also, risks categories, roles and their responsibilities, definition of probability/impact of the risks are defined in order for the processes of "Identify Risks" and "Risk Analysis" to take place.

6.2.1 Risk Categories

In order the risks can be proper identified, the following categories of risks are defined at this stage of the project. Any new category identified through the course of the project will be part of the risk management process.

These are the risk categories identified at this stage of the project:

- Financial risks
- Communications
- Scope
- Cost
- Resources

6.2.2 Roles and Responsibilities

The project Coordinator will lead and supervise the risk management activities in coordination with the Steering Committee.

Other roles involved during the risk management processes with a major responsibility are: Technical Manager and Work Package Leaders.

The next Risk Assessment Matrix (RAM) summarises the roles and responsibilities within the project, according to a RASCI model: The RASCI model **Error! Reference source not found.** describes the participation by various roles in completing tasks or deliverables for a project or business process.

Table 49: Roles and Responsibilities – Risk MGT

RASCI chart	ROLES				
	PC	TC	WPL	TL	Partner
Plan Risk Management	R	C	C	C	S
Identify Risks	A	C	R	C	S
Risk Analysis	A	C	R	C	S
Plan Risk responses	A	C	R	C	S
Control Risks	A	C	R	C	S

- Responsible (R) is the entity(s) who is the owner of the problem, generally the entity that does the work
- Accountable (A) is the entity to whom "R" is accountable and the authority who approves to sign-off on work, there is max 1 entity accountable per task/process
- Supportive (S) is the entity(s) that provides resources or has a supporting role
- Consulted (C) is the entity(s) that provide information and/or expertise necessary to complete the task
- Informed (I) is the entity(s) that needs to be notified of the results but need not necessarily be consulted.

As it can be seen in the RASCI table, Work Package Leaders are the main responsible for the identification of new risks, as well its analysis and classification, Work Package leaders will have the support of Task leaders and partners from the same WP on these tasks.

Once the risks are identified and analysed, and a response plan for each is designed, they will be informed to the Project Coordinator who is the main responsible for the management of all risks identified in the course of the project.

6.2.3 Definitions of probability and impact

As explained in the beginning of this chapter, in order to proceed to the proper analysis of each identified risk, both probability and impact should be defined in the scope of the project.

Probability

The following scale will be used for the project in order to rate a risk probability properly:

Table 50: Scale of Probability

Scale for probability										
Rating	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Interpretation	Low		Medium		Medium-high		High		Fact	

As it can be seen on the table above, there are two numbers for each interpretation, meaning that inside each interpretation you have also degrees, for example, a risk with Low probability can be classified as "very low" (rating 1), or "low" (rating 2), and so on.

Impact

The consortium of ALCHIMIA has agreed on the following types of impact and its correspondent classification:

Impact on the schedule:

Table 51: Impact on schedule

Impact	Classification
Delay of 3 or more months on DoA deadlines (tasks start/end time, deliverables and milestones deadlines) – i.e. Task 1.2 delay will have an impact on task 3.4 start time by 3 months.	9-10
Delay of 2 months on DoA deadlines (tasks start/end time, deliverables and milestones deadlines)	7-8
Delay of 1 month on DoA deadlines (tasks start/end time, deliverables and milestones deadlines)	5-6
Delays on internal deliverables by 1 – 3 months	3-4
Delays on any task or deliverable that does not have impact on other tasks	1-2

Impact on the achievements of results:

Table 52: Impact on results

Impact	Classification
One main objective of ALCHIMIA not achieved, i.e. major impact on DoA, which could lead to an amendment request on the Grant Agreement	9-10
WP objective not fully achieved	7-8
Objectives of more than one Tasks are not achieved	5-6
Task objective not achieved	3-4
Task objective not fully achieved	1-2

6.2.4 Risk Register

The Risk Register is the main result of the Risk Management Process, as it aims to reflect the output of many processes such as Identify Risks and Risk Analysis among others.

This document will be filled through various iterations, having as the main responsible for its management the Project Coordinator.

A separated spreadsheet will be provided for the consortium for this end. The Risk Register has the following fields:

Table 53: ALCHIMIA Risk register fields

Item	Description
Risk ID	The identification for each risk. i.e. R01, R02
Risk	The risk stated in a complete sentence which states the cause of the risk, the risk, and the effect that the risk causes to the project.
Risk Category	Categorization of risks by area of project affected, source of risk or other useful category.
WP related	WP number from which the risk belongs.
Probability	The likelihood that a risk or opportunity will occur.
Impact	The impact of the risk on the project if the risk occurs.
Risk Score	Determined by multiplying probability and impact (scale from 0 to 100).
Risk Response	The action which is to be taken if this risk occurs.
Trigger	Description of an event (or events) that will cause the risk to materialize. Risk Owners should be aware of this information in order they known when to take action.
Risk Owner	The person who the project manager assigns to watch for triggers and manage the risk response if the risk occurs.
Risk Materialized (Y/N)	Information if the risk has already happened.
Status after Response	After the risk response took place, the status should be described.
Overall Status (Open/Closed)	All risks after inserted in the risk register will have the Overall status "open". In case a risk no longer can occur, it should have the status "closed".

As an example we provide in table below a risk of the project to be used for helping in understanding what information must be provided for a risk:

Table 54: ALCHIMIA Risk register

Risk Identification				Qualitative rating			Risk response			Control		
Risk ID (Rx.y)	Risk	Risk Category	WP related	Probability	Impact	Risk Score	Risk Response (Avoid/Mitigation)	Trigger	Risk Owner	Risk Materialized	Status after response	Overall status (open/closed)
R1.1	Ca not signed	Mgt	WP1	0	10	0	Mitigation: Blocking issues to be solved, negotiation and flexibility required.	by each legal conference	ATOS	N	CA signed by all partners	01-Open
R1.2	Unexpected global problem impacting on the project activities (something similar to COVID crisis)	Management	WP1	5	9	45	Analysis is being performed about the possible impact of unexpected situations in the different entities and tasks. Always a substitute for each responsible of each task	By each PCT	ALL	N		01-Open

6.3 Identify Risks

The main output of this process is the list of risks identified by the consortium. Work Package Leaders should provide the project coordinator the following information for this process:

- Risk ID
- Risk
- Risk Category
- WP related

The Project Coordinator will be in charge of coordinating this process, ensuring that the required level of detail of the risks identified is present.

The project should use as starting point the risks that are already present in the DoA.

As all processes inside the Risk Management Process, this is an iterative process that will take place through the project lifetime. All WP leaders are responsible for a regular overview on new risks that could take place and were not foresaw during the start of the project. These new risks should be informed to the Project Coordinator as soon as they appear.

The Project Coordinator also will ensure that a regular communication channel will be open for this end through teleconferences and e-mails (or other communication tools provided).

The project coordinator will also regularly inform the consortium of the status of the Risk Register, informing of any new risks found its impact and the responses agreed.

6.4 Risk Analysis

Before the project can plan any response for the identified risks, it is needed a previous classification of each risk. This classification will be done through an analysis made by WP Leaders, where each risk will be given an impact and probability.

The following columns will be filled due to this process:

- Probability
- Impact
- Risk Score (computed by multiplying impact and probability)
- Risk Ranking (highest equals major risk)

6.5 Plan Risk responses

After the risk analysis take place, the consortium has the sufficient information to provide responses for each risk identified.

For all identified risks, these are the following responses that should be given:

- Responses to eliminate the threats before they happen (Avoid actions)
- Responses to decrease the probability and/or impact of threats (Mitigation actions)

These are the columns to be filled in this process:

- Risk Response (Avoid / Mitigation)
 - Avoid: In case an identified risk could be eliminated, the consortium should then inform on this column of the measures to be taken in order this risk cease to exist to the project (i.e. a risk of not reaching a specific deadline could be terminated if this deadline is changed).
 - Mitigation: in case a risk cannot be eliminated by the moment on its identification and analysis, a contingency plan should be informed along with measures to minimize the probability/impact
- Trigger: an event expected to cause the risk to occur, the risk owner should be aware of this information.
- Risk Owner: Person who will be responsible for the implementation and closure of the mitigating actions assigned to the risk.

It is very important to notice that when planning a response for a risk, the response could also generate a new risk. If this happens, this new risk (called Secondary Risk) should also be noted in the risk register.

6.6 Control Risks

The Project Coordinator will start this process after the project produced a full risk register, with all risks identified, their impact and probability assigned and also all planned responses described.

Control Risks process main goal is to ensure that all risks identified are properly handled by the consortium, as well as to ensure that any new identified risks are updated in the risk register.

The Project Coordinator, Work Package Leaders and risk owners should monitor the risk triggers and the status of all risks. Any new identified risks should be analysed and follow the same process as described in this plan (e.g. identification, analysis, plan risks responses, etc.).

Workarounds

This process also could include the sporadically need of workarounds. Whether a risk that was not previously identified by the consortium materialize, the project should come up with a workaround for this risk and it should also be added to the risk register.

Closing Risks

The Project Coordinator is also responsible for closing risks that are no longer applicable. Any risk that is closed should remain in the risk register.

Main output

The main output of this process will be the data provided in the following columns in the risk register (although other columns could be updated if needed):

- Risk Materialized (Y/N): Information if the risk has already happened.
- Status after Response: In case the response took place, the status of the risk should be stated
- Overall Status (Open/Closed): All risks after inserted in the risk register will have the Overall status "open". In case a risk no longer can occur, it should have the status "closed".

When it happens

Finally, this is an iterative process that should be present on the day-to-day life of the project.

In all ALCHIMIA project meetings (physical or remote) there will be a specific slot for the status of the risks as presented here.

Regular meetings (WP-Task Meetings)

For supporting the project on having an awareness of the importance of identifying new risks, all agendas should have a slot for this end, and in the minutes should be reflected any new risks identified.

If any new risk or update of an existing risk is identified, the Work Package leader should be notified immediately and start the process for compiling the information of the risk.

Following, the Work Package Leader will notify the PC and provide the information of the risk for updating the Risk Register.

6.7 Common Risk Management Errors

The following is a list of common risk management errors that all partners should be aware when managing risks:

- Risk identification is finished without a fully technical knowledge of the project goals
- Risk identification to be done in a very short period of time, resulting in a very short list of identified risks or not enough information for them.
- The risks identified are general, instead of ALCHIMIA project specific risks.
- Risk management process is not given enough time or resources
- Risk management process is not proper explained to the whole consortium

References

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Appendix A Acronyms

Abbreviation / Acronym	Description
AE	Affiliated Entity
AP	Associated Partner
CA	Consortium Agreement
CFS	Certificate on the Financial Statements
CM	Communication Manager
DoA	Description of Action
Dx.y	Deliverable number y, belonging to WP number x
EC	European Commission
EM	Exploitation Manager
ETM	Ethical Manager
FC	Financial Controller
GA	Grant Agreement
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
PB	Plenary Board
PC	Project Coordinator
PIM	Pilot Manager
PL	Pilot Leader
PLB	Pilot Board
PM	Person-month
QA	Quality Assurance
QM	Quality Manager
RASCI	Responsible/Accountable/Supportive/Consulted/Informed
RP	Reporting Period
SC	Steering Committee
SM	Scientific Manager
TC	Technical Coordinator
TL	Task Leader
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Appendix A Internal Review planning

A spreadsheet should be created by the Quality Manager (ALCHIMIA reviewers.xlsx, available in the repository) and agreed by the project consortium. A capture of this spreadsheet can be found here below:

Deliv.	1	2	3	4	4.1	4.2	5	6	7	8
	ATOS	SSSA	BFI	CEL	CEL-BCN	CEL-PL	EXUS	FDT	MI	CAR
WP1	X	X	X							
D1.1.- Project Handbook (M3)	E	1								
D1.2.- Data Management Plan (M6)	1	E								
WP2	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
D2.1.- Requirements and human-centric recommendations (M12)								1		E
D2.2.- ALCHIMIA architecture (M24)	E									1
D2.3.- Training Programme (M27)				1						E
WP3	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		
D3.1.- Federated Learning framework_version 1 (M12)	E	1								
D3.2.- Federated Learning framework_final version (M30)	E		1							
WP4	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
D4.1.- Holistic process models and XAI (M18)		1	E							
D4.2.- LCA and optimisation frameworks (M24)		E	1							
WP5	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
D5.1.- Use-cases preparation (M12)	1			E						
D5.2.- Integration, validation and evaluation in ALCHIMIA use-cases (M36)				E					1	
WP6	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
D6.1.- Plan for impact creation and standardisation (M36)		1								E
D6.2.- Business and exploitation plan report (M36)			1							E
D6.3.- Environmental Impact Assessment (M36)		1								E

Figure 8 – ALCHIMIA reviewers spreadsheet capture

All deliverables are listed in the first column, while all ALCHIMIA partners are listed in the first row; an “E” in the cell indicates that the partner is the editor of the deliverable, while a “1” in the cell indicates that the partner is a reviewer of the document. In the figure above, for example, the deliverable D1.1, due in month M3, will be reviewed by SSSA.

This spreadsheet may be modified if needed according to the evolution of the project.

Appendix B Peer review form

Below are the items to be checked in the Peer Review Form:

ELEMENT TO REVIEW	Y	N	NA	COMMENTS
FORMAT: Does the document ... ?				
...include deliverable name, version number, dissemination level and date?				
...include the names of contributors and reviewers?				
...contain a revision table with the responsible person for each version?				
... contain an updated table of contents?				
... contain a list of abbreviations?				
... contain an Executive Summary?				
... contain a reference list?				
... use the fonts and sections defined in the official template?				
... use correct spelling and grammar?				
... conform to length guidelines (50 pages maximum (plus Executive Summary and annexes)				
... contain a conclusion section?				

CONTENT:	Y	N	NA	COMMENTS
Is the content presented in a clear way and logical order?				
Is the Executive Summary <u>self contained</u> and includes the main conclusions of the document?				
Does the content of the document match the description in the <u>DoW</u> ?				
Are the contents of the document treated with the required depth?				
Does the document need additional sections to be considered complete?				
Are there any sections in the document that should be removed?				
Are all references in the document included in the references list?				

Suggested Improvements

PAGE	SECTION	SUGGESTED IMPROVEMENT
		ADD ROWS AS NECESSARY

Conclusion:

	Document <u>accepted</u> , no changes required.
	Document <u>accepted</u> , changes required.
	Document <u>not accepted</u> , it must be reviewed after changes are implemented

Figure 9 – ALCHIMIA peer review form